

ROLE OF YONIDHUPAN IN VAGINAL INFECTIONS**¹Dr. Trupti Kale, ²Dr. Seema Mehare**¹Phd Scholar Dept. of Prasutitantra Streerog Y.M.T Ayurved Medical College and Hospital.²Guide and H.O.D.Y.M.T Ayurved Medical College and Hospital.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Trupti Kale**

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ABSTRACT

Sthanik Chikitsa Is The Special Local Therapy Mentioned In Ayurveda Classics in Different Yonivyapada (Genital Disorders), Yoniroga, Santatinirodha, T and For Maintainance of Genital Health. Different Types of Sthanik Chikitscha mentioned yonidhawan, yonidhupan, yonipichu, yonikalka, yonilepa, yonipinda, yonivarti, yonidhoopan, ksharkarma, uttarbasti.

INTRODUCTION

Yonidhupan Means The Fumigation Of Vulva And Vagina Is The Special Local Therapy Mentioned In Ayurveda Classics In Different Yonivyapada, Gynelological Disorders Maintain sterilized external and internal environment of genitals. Drugs with katu, tikta, kashay ras and laghu, ruksha and ushna properties are described by ayurvedic acharyas. Dhupan dravyas on heating get converted into fumes causes dilatation and oxidation of blood vessels and increases tissue perfusion. Leading to antiseptic and sterilized environment of vagina. Yonidhupana having kandughna, krimighna, vranopak activities has bacteriostatic, antimicrobial activities it is economical, easy to perform and having no side effects.

Vaginal Infections Like Atrophic Vaginitis, Candidiasis, Trichomoniasis, Yeast.

Infections, Unusual Vaginal Discharge And Sti Sexually Transmitted Infections.

Routinely we see these patients in opd even after having allopathic tretment they are recurrently having vaginal discharge, irritation. Ayurveda explains the treatment of yonirogas starts with nidanparivarjan, shodhan, shaman and sthanik chikitcha. The way gudbasti acts on pakvashaya and cures all the chronic disorders in body sthanik chikitchas have direct action on garbhashaya and treat the garbhashaygat doshas and completely improves these conditions.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To study the use of sthanik chikitSa yonidhupan in treatment of vaginal infections.

OBJECTIVES

To study sthanik chikitsa from various ayurvedic text articalEs.

To study the procedure of sthanik chikitsa yonidhupan.

To study probable mode of action of sthanik chikitsa.

DHOOPAN

Different types of Dhoopana drugs On the basis of origin “Avum Dhoopa Samutpanna Prajanam Hitkamya / Nirdishtascha Agnidaitvya Jangam Sthavaraashrya //” (K.S.Dh.kalp)

1. Jangama: Animal origin (Hairs, nails, horns, sarpnirmoka etc.) Animal product contains a keratin like structural part that contains sulphur play a key role in disinfection.
2. Sthavara: Plant origin (Agaru, vacha, haridra, kustha, guggulu nimba etc.)
3. Minerals: Harital & Manahshila. These are the Sulphur containing compounds According to Acharya Kashyapa10: Dhoopa, Anudhoopa, Pratidhoopa.

All these drugs are collected and stored in air-tight containers like earthen pots and glass jars to maintain its original colour and volatile oil contents.

1. Properties of Dhoopan drugs^[11]

: Guna: Laghu,

Ruksha, Tikshna, Vikasi, Uragandhi, Volatile; Rasa: Katu, Tikta; Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu; Karma: Shothahara, Krimighana, Kandughana, Vranasho-dhana, Vranaropan, Vedanashamaka; Mahabhoota pradhanya: Akasha, Vayu Purpose of Dhoopan.

Rakshoghana karama

: Dhoopan of bhesajagar, kumaragara, sutikagara, Shastrakaram-gruha.

2. Vyadhinashana^[13]

For vranashodhana, vranaropan, kledashoshana, krimihara, ve-danashamak, durgandhahara etc.

3. Sterilization of asava and arishata

Kaala: "Dwiraha karyed dhoopan dashratram atandrita^[14],"

/(Su.S.) Dhoopan is advised in morning and evening for 10 days for 3-5 minutes.

YONI + DHOOPANA

Means fumigation of vulva and vagina.

Yonidhoopana is a practical procedure in which fumigation of vulva & vagina is performed by medicated and disinfected smoke over the surface of yoni. It is indicated as Rakshoghana and Vyadhi chikitsa in striroga and prasuta. Vagina is preferred as a route of drug delivery due to its large surface area, high vascularity and permeability to absorb the medicated fumes or any medicated drug kept in vagina.

COMMONLY USED DRUGS FOR YONIDHAVAN IN VAGINAL INFECTIONS

Sarala Yava

Guggulu

Bruhatiphala Haridra Daruharida Sarshapa Kushta

Agaru

Mode Of Action Of Yonidhupan

Mode of action of Yonidhoopana: Dhoopan drugs with katu-tikta ushan and aromatic properties when put on fire get converted into volatile medicated fumes. These fumes enter into smallest units of tissues of genital tract (due to sooksham-srotogami), dilates blood vessels and helps in oxidation of blood that leads to adequate tissue perfusion. This antiseptic & sterilized environment helps in disinfection of uterine cavity, vagina & vulva; reduces PH & laxity of pubic muscles. Thus helps in reducing pain, decreasing vaginal discharge, healing of wound & prevent growth of microorganisms.

CONCLUSION

Dhoopana drugs having katu-tikta, laghu-ruksha, tikshna-ushna properties and volatile contents proved to be kandughna, kledashoshaka, vranaropaka, shothahara, jantughna, vedanashamaka. Yonidhoopana Means fumigation of vulva-vagina has shown significant effect in different genital disorders, sutika, sukha-Prasava and improves defence mechanism of female Genital tract by maintaining healthy vaginal flora. Various drugs has

shown antimicrobial action against E.coli, Staphylococcus aureus, S. bony, Candida albicans. Therefore, yonidhoopana has bacteriostatic action, economical, effective procedure and easy to perform without any harmful effects.

REFERENCES

1. Dr. sushila Sharma, abhinavastri roga Vigyana, edition 1st, Ayurveda sanskrita Hindi pustaka bhandara, Jaipur, 2016.
2. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Charaka-Samhita with the Ayurvedadipika Commentary by Chakrapanidutta, edited by Jadavji Trikambaji Acharya, Choukhamba Surbharati Prakashana, Varanasi, 2013.
3. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita with Nibandha Samgraha Commentary by Sri Dal-Hanaacharya, edited by Jadavji Trikambaji Acharya, from the beginning of 9th Adhyaya of Chikitsa Sthana And the rest by Narayan Ram Acharya Kavyatirtha, edition 2013, Choukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi.
4. Vagbhata, Ashtanga Hridaya, with commentaries of Arunadatta & Hemadri, edited By Bhishgaacharya Harishastri Paradakara, 9th edition, Choukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi, 2005.
5. Vagbhata, Ashtanga Samgraha with Hindi Commentary, by Kaviraj Atrideva Gupta, Edition 2011, Choukhamba Krishnadas Academy.
6. Tiwari P. Ayurveda Prasuti tantraevam Stri Roga. 1st ed. Varanasi. Choukhamba Orientalia, 2007; 2.
7. Healingearth.co.in/yonipichu.
8. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Govinda Das with Vidyotanihindi commentary by ShriAmbika DuttaShastri, Choukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, 11th Edition.
9. Indradev Tripathi and Dr. Daya Shankar Tripathi, Yoga Rathnakara, Vaidyaprabha Hindi commentary, Chap-Sthana Roga Chikitsa/189, edition-first, 1998, Published, By Krishnadas Academy, Varanasi.